

Extended Data: Content theme vocabulary per training area (PATTERN Task 1.1)

Project: PATTERN – Piloting open and responsible Activities and Trainings Towards the Enhancement of Researchers Networks

Work Package: WP1

Task: Task 1.1 – Mapping and analysis of training activities

Funding: Horizon Europe (Grant Agreement No. 101094416)

Project context

This document presents the content theme vocabulary developed within the Horizon Europe project *Piloting open and responsible Activities and Trainings Towards the Enhancement of Researchers Networks* (PATTERN). The vocabulary was produced to support Task 1.1 (Mapping and analysis of training activities) within Work Package 1 (WP1), which aimed to systematically identify, categorise, and analyse training resources related to Open and Responsible Research and Innovation (Open RRI).

The development of a structured and shared content vocabulary was essential to ensure consistency in the mapping process, facilitate comparative analysis across training areas, and support the identification of thematic coverage and gaps. The vocabulary provided a common framework for describing the topics addressed by training resources across multiple Open RRI domains.

The work was carried out under the leadership of Aarhus University (AU) and involved contributions from the following PATTERN consortium members: Aarhus University, European Science Foundation (ESF), Sissa – International School for Advanced Studies (SISSA), Learning Planet Institute (LPI), OpenAIRE, European Association of Research Managers and Administrators (EARMA), Università Vita-Salute San Raffaele (UniSR), DANS – Data Archiving and Networked Services, Ruđer Bošković Institute (RBI), SciLink, and Universidade do Minho (UMinho).

The content themes draw on a combination of existing frameworks and project-specific expertise: The Citizen Science content themes were adopted from the TIME4CS project and the Research Integrity themes were derived from the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity and the Standard Operating Procedures for Research Integrity (SOPs4RI) taxonomy. Other thematic areas were developed collaboratively by domain experts within the consortium.

Content theme vocabulary table

ORRI training area	Content theme vocabulary
Open Access	Copyrights, Funder Requirements, Open Access, Predatory Publishing, Preprint Servers, Publishing Lifecycle, Repository, Research Evaluation, Rights Retention Strategy, Scholarly Publishing
FAIR data and Research Data Management (RDM)	Data Archiving, Data Discovery, Data Management, Ethics, FAIR, Open Access, Open Data, Open Science, Quality Assessment, Reusing Data, Sharing Data
Citizen Science	Best Practices, Citizen Science Stories, Co-creation, Communication, Data Quality and Standards, Empowerment, Engagement, Evaluation of Citizen Science, Event Planning, Funding, Impact, Institutional Change, Introduction to Citizen Science, Link with Formal Education, Project Management, Project Sustainability, Reflections on Science, Regulations and Ethics, Research Design and Methods
Research Integrity	Biomedical Ethics, Data Practices and Management, Declaration of Interests, Ethical Review, Informed Consent, Intellectual Property Rights and Authorship, Moral-Compass: Values-Based Trainings, Open Science, Privacy and Confidentiality, Publication and Communication, Research Collaborations, Research Environment, Research Ethics, Research Integrity, Research Misconduct and Questionable Research Practices, Responsible Research and Good Scientific Practice, Supervision and Mentoring, Vulnerable Participants
Gender, Non-discrimination and Inclusion in Research	Diversity, Gender-Based Violence, Gender Budgeting, Gender Dimension, Gender Equality, Gender Equality Plan, Gender Sensitive Research, Inclusion, Intersectionality
Dissemination and Exploitation of Results	Business Plans, Business/Go-to-Market, Communication and Dissemination Plans, Copyright, Entrepreneurship, Industry Collaborations, Intellectual Property, Investments and Funding, Market Analysis, Multimedia, Proof-of-Concept Experiments, Public Speaking, Regulatory Affairs, Scientific and Technical Writing, Social and Economic Impact, Social Media & Digital Communication, Strategy, Team Creation, Technology Transfer, Tools for Presentation
Science Communication (towards media and policy makers)	Communicating AI, Communication with Policy Makers, Environmental Communication, Event Organisation, Health Communication, Institutional Communication & Public Relations, Media Training, Multimedia, Publishing, Risk Communication, Science Communication Theory, Science Journalism, Science Museums & Science Centres, Science Policy, Social Media & Digital Communication
Management and Leadership	Build Mentor-Mentee Relationships, Coaching/Supporting and Leading Change, Communication Styles and Strategies, Conflict

	Resolution, Cope with Pressure, Empowerment, Leadership, Managing Performance, Networking/Career Development, Problem Solving, Project Management, Project Sustainability, Promote Inclusion and Diversity, Recruitment, Resources Management, Self-Organisation, Strategic Thinking, Team Development
Open Science	Citizen Science, IPR and Legal Skills, Open Access, Open Data, Open Educational Resources, Open Methodology, Open Notebooks, Open Peer Review, Open Reproducible Research, Open Science Definition, Open Science Evaluation, Open Science Guidelines, Open Science Policies, Open Science Projects, Open Science Tools, Open Software/Open Source, Research Integrity and OS, Train the Trainer
General Open RRI training	Citizen Science, Diversity and Inclusion, Dissemination, Exploitation, FAIR Data, Gender, Governance, Implementing RRI, Management and Leadership, Open Access, Open Science, Organisational Support for OS, RDM, Reproducibility in Research, Research Integrity, Science Communication and Public Engagement
Collections, catalogues, platforms	Citizen Science, Dissemination & Exploitation, FAIR Data, Management and Leadership, Open Access, Open Science, Policy, RDM, Research Evaluation, Research Integrity, Science Communication